

NITRO: an Interconnected 5G-IoT Cyber Range

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents NITRO cyber range, which aims at creating a specialized cybersecurity testing and training environment for 5G and IoT networks. NITRO provides a platform for researchers and security professionals to simulate real-world scenarios, assess vulnerabilities, and validate security measures. It focuses on identifying novel cascading attacks that exploit the interdependencies between devices. Another innovation of the NITRO platform is the adversarial AI exercises on 5G and IoT networks, aiming at raising awareness of the vulnerabilities of AI models, how they can be attacked and how robust AI can defend against these vulnerabilities. The overarching goal of NITRO is to enhance security of 5G and IoT networks and serve as a precursor to the development of new cyber ranges within critical infrastructure sectors.

KEYWORDS

Cyber range, adversarial AI, Internet of Things, 5G

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1 INTRODUCTION

The fifth generation of mobile networks (5G) offer several new services that enhance speed, connectivity and reliability, enabling innovative and data-centric applications such as real-time data processing and analysis. The above services of 5G also enable massive and robust IoT deployments, giving rise to interconnected 5G-IoT networks that can be utilized in various industries from healthcare to intelligent transportation and supply chain. Nevertheless, this collaboration also brings new cybersecurity challenges that require our attention, since new operational frameworks are needed to comprehend the 5G-IoT threat landscape.

A cyber range is a relatively new approach to enhance preparedness and at the same time provide specialized training. We argue that a cyber range can provide an environment for developing the skills and strategies needed to secure 5G-IoT networks effectively. As 5G-IoT networks involve complex, interconnected systems, a cyber range can simulate this complexity, providing realistic scenarios for training. Moreover, cyber ranges offer flexibility since it can be customized to replicate specific 5G-IoT environments, from smart cities to industrial IoT applications. All in all, a cyber range can help the security community respond to the emerging threats that come along with the emerging 5G-IoT networks.

Despite the technical advances in cyber ranges, several issues still need to be addressed. First, while cyber ranges have gained popularity in various sectors, including government, military, and academia, their adoption within critical infrastructure organizations has been relatively slower [12]. Moreover, there is a clear lack of cyber ranges specialized for adversarial Artificial Intelligence (AI) attacks. Currently, cyber ranges do not provide emulation for attacking AI models through adversarial examples [22]. As a matter of fact, critical infrastructures are vulnerable to this category of attacks as AI is being utilized increasingly last years in several domains such as energy, IoT, and 5G. In the last case, researchers [11] have identified that components of 5G Network Infrastructures are subject to adversarial attacks including the prediction models for channel quality indicator, network slicing, power efficiency, and spectral efficiency that all commonly utilize AI for processing input data and predicting the best strategies. Finally, one prevalent issue is that many cyber ranges do not offer sufficient feedback mechanisms for learners to evaluate their progress and enhance their understanding. While cyber ranges serve as invaluable training

environments, the lack of detailed feedback often hinders learners' ability to gauge their performance and identify areas for improvement. To address this challenge, there is a growing need to prioritize the development of cyber ranges that provide comprehensive and timely feedback.

This paper will deliver a 5G-IoT cyber range named NITRO, which refers to a specialized cybersecurity testing and training environment that focuses on simulating and evaluating the security of 5G networks interconnected with IoT devices and applications. NITRO will provide a controlled platform where cybersecurity professionals, researchers, and organizations will be able to study, practice, and develop skills related to securing 5G mobile networks, IoT wireless technologies and their interconnection. Moreover, this platform will examine and identify novel cascading attacks that can exploit the interdependencies between various devices, systems, and network elements in interconnected 5G and IoT networks leading to a domino effect of compromised systems. On top of these, NITRO will deliver a novel set of exercises that consider adversarial AI attacks and their detection, contributing in this way to this emerging interdisciplinary field of AI and cybersecurity. Overall, the NITRO's objectives are presented below:

- Deliver a novel cybersecurity platform for virtualised 5G-IoT cyber range services for improving the security of standalone and interconnected 5G and IoT environments. To this end, integration of existing testbeds for IoT and 5G will be considered in order to create a unique new environment for security training as defined by NITRO project.
- To create the first common Data Repository for 5G-IoT cyber ranges that will include attacks, threat analysis, scenarios, for both 5G and IoT networks. Open standards for interoperability will be utilized (such as XML and JSON) to define the metadata structure. The NITRO knowledge repository [21], through a suitable open-data access policy, will be a novel and unique instrument for knowledge transfer and big data analytics playground.
- NITRO will offer a powerful training environment for improving the preparedness of professionals (from staff in security operation centres to pen testers) through a variety of exercises. NITRO's innovative virtual cyberwarfare training environment will help the next generation of cyber defenders advance their cybersecurity skills and better prepare to detect, block and mitigate emerging cyberattacks by testing and evaluating, under high-stress, and real-world conditions, security technologies and methodologies, including virtualised versions of IDS/IPS, penetration testing tools, etc.
- To emulate innovative AI adversarial attacks that can drive impactful attacks on 5G and IoT networks management structures along with detection capabilities testing

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 will discuss the threats and risks that 5G and IoT networks face. Section 3 presents the NITRO Cyber range platform and its objectives. Section 4 elaborates on the technologies that will be utilized for the implementation of the cyber range. Section 5 presents NITRO's contributions towards EU directives and finally section 6 concludes the article.

2 THREAT LANDSCAPE OF 5G AND IOT NETWORKS

In this section we elaborate on the threats and risks that 5G and IoT networks face. First, it is evident that new technologies introduced in 5G can lead to opportunities for new attack vectors which are not well studied. The 5G requirements for optimization of data rate, delay, and connection numbers have led to new technologies, such as bulk configuration, and network slicing. Indicatively, network slicing is a form of virtualisation, based on principles akin to Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualisation (NFV). By enabling multi-tenancy and support for multiple services and in a dynamic manner, network slicing has evolved into a fundamental concept in 5G. At the same time, it constitutes an opportunity for new types of threats, such as time impersonation attacks against the network slice manager [13] or network slice instances. The provision of different security protocols and policies in different slices may also produce new challenges, accentuated by the multi-tenant nature of 5G.

Apart from network slicing, another important feature of 5G networks is related to the fact that the 5G Core functions are meant to be largely composed of applications running on general purpose hardware that communicate through application programming interfaces (APIs). The integrity of the software, especially from open-source locations and the overall software supply chain, is an area of vulnerability. As services can be created, destroyed, and communicate with each other dynamically, systems must be properly authenticated and communications protected in order to prevent unauthorized execution of functions or access to data [9].

IoT networks have their own set of threats and risks that can be exploited by adversaries to compromise the security of IoT applications and systems [24]. For instance, there are multiple CVEs assigned to IoT protocols such as: MQTT Packet Crafting Attack (CVE-2016-10523), MQTT Publish Flood (CVE-2018-1684), CoAP Segmentation Fault Attack (CVE-2019-12101) and CoAP Memory Leak Attack (CVE-2019-9004). More critically, IoT devices have limited memory and processing capabilities, a fact that reduces the security mechanisms that can be integrated to upscale the security of these devices.

Finally, interconnection of 5G with IoT devices may lead to cascading attacks by chaining vulnerabilities. By providing connectivity to an unprecedented number of small and insecure IoT devices, 5G networks may experience high occurrence of security breaches either originating from these devices or targeting them to cause adverse effects in physical space. The potential large-scale physical impact caused by remotely controlling or passively monitoring a large number of IoT devices will be very attractive to escalating cyber threats.

3 NITRO CYBER RANGE

NITRO aims to contribute and foster the creation of a 5G-IoT cyber range (see Figure 1) which refers to a specialized cybersecurity testing and training environment that focuses on simulating and evaluating the security of 5G networks in conjunction with Internet of Things (IoT) devices and applications. It provides a controlled platform where cybersecurity professionals, researchers, and organizations can study, practice, and develop skills related to securing

5G networks, IoT technologies as well as their interconnection. NITRO will leverage existing software, tools and methodologies towards the implementation of the platform software components as well as utilize existing cyber ranges to integrate and deliver a unique and - first of its kind - novel 5G-IoT cyber range. Also, NITRO will design and implement real-world attack and defence scenarios, allowing stakeholders to understand and address the unique security challenges that arise from the convergence of 5G and IoT. Finally, NITRO will consider adversarial AI attacks and their detection, being of the first cyber ranges that will emulate attacks on AI models for training and security testing. More specifically, the aims of NITRO are as follows:

Figure 1: NITRO architectural blueprint

A1: Deliver a novel cyber range platform that offers a simulated environment to test, analyze, and refine the security aspects of 5G networks and IoT interconnected networks. NITRO will provide a comprehensive platform for researchers, engineers, and security professionals to simulate real-world scenarios, assess vulnerabilities, and validate security measures in a pedagogical manner. The cyber range enables the emulation of diverse 5G network architectures, IoT device configurations, and communication protocols, allowing for in-depth analysis of potential threats and attack vectors. To this end, NITRO plays a crucial role in enhancing the cybersecurity of critical infrastructures in line with the objectives of the NIS Directive and specifically in the area of telecommunications and IoT domain applications (e.g., Industry 4.0,

supply chain, smart cities). As privacy of personal data in cyber ranges is of utmost importance, a privacy toolbox will be utilized to examine and identify potential GDPR issues within the NITRO cyber range.

- A2:** Examine and identify novel cascading attacks that can leverage vulnerabilities in different components and exploit the interdependencies between various devices, systems, and network elements in 5G and IoT networks. Supply chains, network infrastructure, device compromise and protocol exploitation are prime targets of adversaries that can be exploited, leading to a domino effect of compromised systems. This objective will facilitate trainees to comprehend the insidious threats coming from the integration of critical systems and to design more secure 5G-IoT and in general interconnected systems.
- A3:** Deliver the first of its kind cyber range for adversarial AI attack and defence exercises, contributing in this way to this emerging interdisciplinary field of AI and cybersecurity. In particular, it will provide a controlled platform to simulate and study various adversarial techniques and strategies that can undermine the performance or integrity [23, 25] of AI algorithms as they are applied in 5G and IoT networks. Apart from increasing awareness for the dangers lurking from adversarial AI, more importantly NITRO will enable the development and validation of AI models that are more robust, secure, and capable of withstanding malicious attempts to manipulate the behaviour of the models. As such, the overarching goal is to enable researchers and practitioners to enhance their understanding of adversarial AI techniques and explore strategies for building more secure AI systems. A set of open source and off-the-shelf datasets will be utilized in NITRO to deploy adversarial attacks including the DeepSlice dataset, and the Secure5G dataset [2, 26, 27] as well as for IoT networks including WSN-DS [8, 10] and CICIDS18 [28].
- A4:** NITRO will create the NITRO Data Repository designed to capture, organize, and manage information pertaining to threats, vulnerabilities, and security incidents specifically targeting 5G networks and IoT ecosystems. It will serve as a critical resource for security practitioners, researchers, and organizations, enabling comprehensive tracking, analysis, and response to emerging threats and real-world incidents. By correlating this information, it will provide valuable insights into the evolving threat landscape of 5G-IoT interconnected networks and assist in devising effective mitigation strategies. Through its incident tracking and reporting capabilities, the NITRO repository facilitates incident response, forensics analysis, and the dissemination of best practices and lessons learned, fostering a proactive approach to maintaining the security and resilience of 5G-IoT environments. To generate, collect and organize this dataset, an automated tool for generating the related traffic will be leveraged aiming to integrate contemporary technologies for automated security validation and verification as well as security emulation and testing in 5G networks.

4 IMPLEMENTATION

According to 3GPP, the 5G System (5GS) has three main components:

- (1) User Equipment (UE)
- (2) 5G Radio Access Network (5G-RAN), also known as gNB
- (3) 5G Core Network (5GC)

UEs are devices enabled with 5G (user equipment), while 5G-RAN is in essence the radio base stations that wirelessly connects user equipment to a core network. The 5G Core network facilitates various Network Functions (NFs) such as session management, authentication, policy control, data storage etc.

Figure 2: 5G deployment and key components

For the implementation of the 5G system, the key technologies that are to be adopted in NITRO are presented below:

- Next Generation Node B (gNB): The 5G base station that provides radio access to user equipment, enabling wireless communication with the core network. Consider that eNB (evolved Node B) was part of LTE networks, while gNB is specifically designed for 5G networks.
- Network Slice Selection Function (NSSF): Responsible for the selection of network slices, which are virtualized network partitions tailored for different service requirements, ensuring efficient resource utilization.

- Network Exposure Function (NEF): Facilitates the exposure of network services and capabilities to external applications and systems through APIs, enabling innovative service integration.
- Network Repository Function (NRF): Maintains a repository of all the network functions within the 5G core network, supporting their registration, discovery, and status management.
- Policy Control Function (PCF): Manages and enforces policies related to quality of service (QoS), access control, and charging rules, ensuring optimal network performance and user experience.
- Unified Data Management and Repository (UDM and UDR): Responsible for centralized management of subscriber data. It stores user profiles, authentication details, service subscriptions, and policies.
- Application Function (AF): Represents external applications that interact with the 5G core network, providing service-specific functionalities and leveraging network capabilities.
- Authentication Server Function (AUSF): Manages the authentication of user devices, ensuring secure access to network services through robust authentication mechanisms.
- AMF (Access and Mobility Management Function): Handles user access and mobility management, including connection setup, handover, and registration procedures.
- Session Management Function (SMF): Oversees session management tasks, such as establishing, modifying, and terminating user sessions, ensuring efficient data flow control.
- User Plane Function (UPF): Manages user data traffic routing, forwarding, and processing, playing a crucial role in maintaining data paths from the user equipment to the internet or application servers.
- Packet Data Unit Session (PDU Session): Refers to the sessions established for data communication between user equipment and the data network, enabling internet access and application connectivity.
- 5G User-Plane (U-Plane): handles the direct transmission of user data like internet traffic, voice, and video. It manages data processing, routing, and traffic control between UE and external networks, ensuring efficient and high-speed data delivery. The key component is the UPF, which processes data packets and applies QoS policies.
- 5G Control-Plane (C-Plane): Manages signaling and control messages to establish, maintain, and terminate data connections in 5G networks. It oversees session management, mobility, authentication, security, and policy enforcement for smooth network operations. Key functions include the AMF, SMF, PCF, AUSF, and UDM for managing subscriber data and profiles.

The most important component of NITRO cyber range is undoubtedly the 5G core network. Since most components of 5G core are software applications (i.e. network functions), they can be loaded and run in commodity Linux based machines. As such, there are specific open source implementations that NITRO will utilize, that is: Free5GC [3] and Open5GS [4]. Free5GC is an open-source 5GC software developed in Go [6], adhering to the 3GPP Release

[1] 15 specifications. It operates under the Apache 2.0 license, allowing any individual or organization to use free5GC for commercial products. One unique network function of free5GC compared to other open-source 5GC solutions is the non-3GPP Inter-Working Function (N3IWF). N3IWF connects untrusted non-3GPP devices, such as Wi-Fi Access Points and LoRaWAN Gateways, to the 5GC [17].

Free5GC offers container image releases to facilitate its usage and provides a Docker Compose file for automated network function deployment. Additionally, the contributors of free5GC have maintained a list of articles, studies, and tutorials for those new to the platform. The latest version of Free5GC is 3.4.1. The alternative open-source solution is Open5GS written in C language. It comes with a Web application for managing UE subscription information, suitable for testing. The implementation of Open5GS is based on the 3GPP specifications Release 17 [5], with a rich set of supported features such as IPv6 support, the capability to handle multiple PDU sessions, handover functions, and integration of Voice over LTE and Voice over 5G New Radio. Compared to other 5GC projects, Open5GS benefits from a larger contributor base, resulting in weekly commits to its repository and more frequent software releases. However, Open5GS does not offer official releases of container images for Open5GS's components; thus, users have to build images if they want to deploy them in container-based environments.

The second most important part of the 5G system is the RAN and UE. These components are crucial for providing a genuine 5G network emulation environment, essential for hands-on cybersecurity training. These components will be covered by UERANSIM [7], an open source implementation of 5G UE and 5G RAN (gNodeB). UERANSIM supports to run with Open5GS and Free5GC 5G Core networks. There are 3 main interfaces implemented by UERANSIM:

- (1) Control Interface (between RAN and AMF)
- (2) User Interface (between RAN and UPF)
- (3) Radio Interface (between UE and RAN)

While the above tools can emulate efficiently the 5G system, NITRO requires also a tool to generate and simulate network traffic. This requirement will be covered by an open-source 5G network traffic fuzzer named 5Greplay. The latter is designed to evaluate 5G components by replaying, modifying 5G network traffic, and injecting network scenarios into a target, which can be a 5G service such as Core Network (e.g., AMF, SMF) or a RAN network (e.g., gNodeB).

5 NITRO CONTRIBUTIONS TO EU DIRECTIVES

NITRO will significantly contribute not only to implement but also advance EU directives. More specifically, NITRO's contribution are presented below:

First, NITRO will place great emphasis on education and training, catering to both experts and non-experts. Aligned with the recommendations of SRIA [14], this pillar utilizes a serious game environment and hands-on exercises to enhance the practical skills of trainees, allowing them to develop real-world proficiency in the field.

NITRO will also provide contributions to the EU 5G toolbox [15]. The latter is a set of robust and comprehensive measures for a coordinated EU approach to secure 5G networks. NITRO serves as a crucial component for testing and evaluating the security of 5G networks and associated technologies. By providing a simulated environment that replicates real-world scenarios, NITRO allows for comprehensive testing of potential vulnerabilities and threats, enabling the development and validation of robust security measures. Within the EU toolbox for 5G security, the NITRO Cyber Range acts as a key resource to enhance the security posture of 5G networks across Europe. It facilitates the identification of vulnerabilities, the assessment of risks [17, 18], and the implementation of effective countermeasures. Through hands-on training, exercises, and simulations, stakeholders can strengthen their understanding of 5G security challenges and improve their incident response capabilities.

NITRO also addresses high-level strategic goals and challenges identified by the European Commission. First and foremost, the NIS Directive and NIS 2 Directive [16] are one of the key targets of NITRO as the latter is aligned with the core requirements of these directives as it will deliver, amongst others, a state-of-the-art 5G-IoT cyber range solution that can i) enhance the level of security not only for 5G and 5G/IoT connected networks but also other critical infrastructures by training professionals to identify complex and cascading security attacks that can be enabled only in such systems ; ii) enabling the delivery of innovative solutions for cyber defenders [20] to improve their skills through hands-on practical training individually, or by means of cyberwar games with their peers. Based on the same goal sets, NITRO recognizes the importance of the CER Directive in improving the resilience of critical infrastructure and networks in the EU, and will contribute to the achievement of its objectives, by virtue of the provision of environments capable to train cyber defenders in realistic cyberattack scenarios involving several critical entities.

Securing and evaluating the trustworthiness of AI models will be another strategic contribution of NITRO, fully aligned with ENISA guidelines and emphasis on the security of AI models in various reports: "Cybersecurity of AI and Standardisation", "Artificial Intelligence and Cybersecurity Research", "Artificial Intelligence Cybersecurity Challenges". NITRO aligns with the goals established by Europe 2020, aiming to achieve two main objectives.

NITRO promotes intelligent growth by fostering an economy driven by innovation. Furthermore, it fosters sustainable growth by providing solutions that possess high potential for user acceptance. NITRO's ambition is to ensure the establishment of a Digital Single Market, which has been recognized as a significant priority for Europe. This aims to cultivate an inclusive digital economy and society throughout Europe, benefiting individuals, consumers, and businesses. As a result, NITRO adheres to and expands upon the economic aspect of the Lisbon strategy by expediting the integration of IT applications and services. This acceleration aims to enhance the competitiveness of the European industrial sector and stimulate overall growth. NITRO strongly aligns with the Digital Single Market policy's focus on "Investing in Network Technologies", specifically targeting the augmentation of trust on the Internet and the safeguarding of privacy [19]. NITRO contributes to the first two action lines of the 2020 EU cybersecurity strategy,

namely towards a) EU resilience, technological sovereignty and leadership and b) building operational capacity to prevent, deter and respond cyberattacks.

6 CONCLUSIONS

This paper presented NITRO, an innovative 5G-IoT cyber range for specialized cybersecurity testing and training environment that focuses on simulating and evaluating the security of 5G networks in conjunction with Internet of Things (IoT) devices and applications. By enabling the emulation of diverse 5G network architectures, IoT device configurations, and communication protocols, NITRO provides a comprehensive platform for researchers and security professionals to simulate real-world scenarios, assess vulnerabilities, and validate security measures.

NITRO's innovative virtual cyberwarfare training environment will help the next generation of cyber defenders advance their cybersecurity skills and better prepare to detect, block, and mitigate emerging cyberattacks by testing and evaluating, under high-stress and real-world conditions, security technologies and methodologies. Novel exercises that include adversarial AI and countermeasures for robust AI will be also considered in the context of 5G and IoT networks. NITRO will significantly contribute to the EU 5G toolbox by providing a simulated environment that replicates real-world scenarios, allowing for comprehensive testing of potential vulnerabilities and threats, enabling the development and validation of robust security measures. In conclusion, NITRO represents a significant step forward in securing the emerging 5G-IoT landscape, addressing the critical need for specialized training and operational frameworks to understand and mitigate cybersecurity challenges in interconnected 5G-IoT networks.

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